

TWO APPLICATIONS FOR TEACHING TELECOMMUNICATION ENGINEERING STUDENTS THE ATMOSPHERIC EFFECTS ON THE OPTICAL CHANNELS. APPLICATIONS IN ASTRONOMY, MECHANICAL ENGINEERING AND TELECOMMUNICATIONS

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Conference Key Areas: *Physics and Engineering Education, Virtual and Remote Labs*

Keywords: *Atmospheric turbulence, Student project, Adaptive Optics, Optical Communications, Student workshop design*

ABSTRACT

Atmospheric turbulence is one of the limiting phenomena in interesting applications and fields such of optical telecommunications and Observational Astronomy. Both Telecommunication and Aerospace Engineering students may encounter those

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applications in their professional careers, thus, there is the necessity to introduce this phenomenon and its impact on those fields at the academic formation stage.

In order to teach students of the principles and effects of the atmospheric turbulence in optical propagation, and to illustrate how to solve these problems, two different applications written in MATLAB© were developed.

In this communication both applications and the theoretical background are presented, and the designed activity for Telecommunication Engineers is shown. Results obtained by students and their experience performing the activity are also presented.

1 INTRODUCTION

The atmospheric variations due to fluctuation of the different meteorological parameters (pressure and temperature) affects the refractive index of air, thus modifying the propagation of optical signals through the atmosphere.

Those variations on the trajectory of the signal have a great impact in Optical Telecommunications and Observational Astronomy, among other fields. Being aware of the growing interest of the optical telecommunications market, and the necessity of improvement of Adaptive Optics technologies, aiming the necessity of enlarge the recruitment of new engineers, and the fact that, typically, atmospheric turbulence is poorly analyzed in the academic formation of such future engineers, a MATLAB®-based application has been developed, in parallel with a computational workshop that has been designed in order to introduce this topic to Telecommunication Engineering students.

This communication summarizes the basis of this application and the future implementation of the said workshop.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Physical basis

To simulate the effect of the atmospheric variability and turbulence on the propagation of a light beam, two basic theories are considered. First, the simulation of the atmospheric turbulence is done by means of the so-called Kolmogorov's theory of atmospheric turbulence.

On the other hand, the diffraction theory of light provides the theoretical mathematical basis for describing the propagation of an optical signal (usually a two-dimensional signal which propagates in the third dimension). As is deeply described in the existing literature, diffraction is, by definition, the deflection of waves around the corners of an obstacle or through the aperture in the region of a geometrical shadow of the obstacle. Thanks to Huygens principle, the diffracting object or slit effectively becomes a secondary source of the propagating wave. This framework is useful for describing two-dimensional light sources and the propagation of its corresponding radiation between different planes.

The combination of both theories allows to the simulation of the propagation of a light beam through atmospheric turbulent layers, hence, allowing the simulation and evaluation of the harmful effects that the beam suffers. Figure 1 shows a schematization of the process that is implemented in the next subsection based on this two mathematical and physical frameworks. Both mathematical descriptions are

widely exposed on the existing literature. The interested reader is referred to [1], [2], [3] and [4].

Fig. 1. Propagation of an optical signal through a turbulent medium. First, an emitting object in 2D is defined (in this example, a circular emitting source). Later, the different phases screens corresponding to several turbulent planes are generated at the corresponding distances z_i from the original plane (the object plane). Finally, the resulting amplitude in the final plane is obtained. This working scheme is valid for both the analysis of the effects of the turbulence on the optical quality of an astronomical observation and for the case of a communication between an optical emitter and its corresponding receiver.

2.2 The application

Applying the above-exposed theories, an application written in MATLAB® was developed.

The software presents two different options for simulations:

- Astronomical observation. This option allows the user to simulate an astronomical observation from a ground-based telescope under different meteorological conditions. Furthermore, this option permits to analyze the wavefront distortion due to turbulence and to implement a correction using Adaptive Optics. See Figure 2.
- Satellite communications. This option permits the simulation of the optical link between a ground station and a satellite, and to analyze the effects of the bad meteorological conditions to such communication. See Figure 3.

3 RESULTS

The application developed for this work is capable of provide interesting computational results for engineering in the fields of Adaptive Optics and Free Space Optical Communications.

As an example, the following figures show the main capabilities/possibilities of analysis of the developed code.

Fig. 2. Main window of the Adaptive Optics application. The software allows to simulate a situation without the implementation of Adaptive Optics and also a solution implementing Adaptive Optics. The program also represents the distorted wavefront.

Fig. 3. Main window of the Optical Communication application. The software allows to evaluate the loss on the signal introduced by the atmospheric turbulence. Furthermore, the application permits the estimation of the optimal path for the propagation of the optical signal.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Using the software presented in this paper, which has been developed during a student final degree project, two different workshops has been designed. First, a workshop to set up the basis of Adaptive Optics and design of such kind of systems for Ground-based telescopes has been designed. Second, a workshop introducing the Optical Communications basis and atmospheric turbulence influence in the optical channel has been written. Both workshops are going to be performed in next months, with the participation of Telecommunication and Aerospace Engineering students. A future work will present the early results obtained with the software and the students' feedback.

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